

Earth Observation Satellite Scheduling with Graph Neural Networks

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The Earth Observation Satellite Planning (EOSP) problem involves scheduling requested observations on an agile satellite while adhering to visibility windows and operational constraints, and selecting a subset of observations to maximize their cumulative benefit. Traditional approaches rely on heuristic and iterative search algorithms. This paper introduces a new technique using Graph Neural Networks and Deep Reinforcement Learning to select and schedule observations efficiently. The proposed method extracts relevant information from EOSP graphs and leverages reinforcement learning for scheduling. Experiments demonstrate that the technique learns effectively on small instances and generalizes well to larger, real-world instances, outperforming traditional learning-based methods.

1 Introduction

The Earth observation satellite (EOS) problem involves acquiring photographs of various locations on Earth's surface to satisfy multiple user requests [1]. Agile EOS satellites, which have degrees of freedom in pitch and roll, can target locations beyond their vertical (nadir) point. In low orbit, each observation is available in a visible time window (VTW) longer than its acquisition duration, but maneuvering between observations involves delays due to attitude adjustments. The EOS is typically oversubscribed, meaning there are more observations to be performed than time available, and different acquisitions have varying priorities or utilities. The goal of the EOS problem (EOSP) is to select and schedule acquisitions to maximize their cumulative values while respecting operational constraints. Due to its complexity and NP-completeness, which make optimal schedules for large instances impractical, most research has focused on approximate and heuristic algorithms.

Because the satellites tasks are operationally scheduled orbit per orbit and satellite by satellite for agile Very High Resolution satellites, this paper addresses

an EOSP version involving a single satellite to be scheduled over a single orbit. A simplification is made in this work compared to the operational constraints: only single-shot acquisitions are considered within their VTWs. Building on the trend of using deep learning in combinatorial optimization, specifically Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL), the study adapts a state-of-the-art combination of graph neural networks (GNN) and DRL, originally developed for Job Shop Scheduling Problems [2], to the EOSP. This approach, named Wheatley, demonstrates superior performance compared to current state-of-the-art techniques, especially in solving deterministic but largely oversubscribed problems.

Our main contributions are: 1. to propose a graph search representation of EOSP without discretizing time, 2. to use graph representation as observations and 3. to use deep reinforcement learning to solve the problem.

Our main results are that the obtained schedules are very competitive to the best baselines and that the system generalizes finding solutions to larger instances, while training on smaller ones.

We describe our approach for solving EOSP in Section 2. Section 3 is dedicated to the results presentation. We conclude in Section 4.

2 EOSP Problem Solving

2.1 Problem Formulation

An instance of the EOSP is defined by a set of n candidate observations, or acquisitions, and a time-horizon τ (in this work, the duration of an orbit). Each observation i is associated with its duration d_i and its VTW $[e_i; l_i]$. The transition duration between two acquisitions i and j is a function $\Delta_{i,j}(t_i)$ of the starting time t_i of the first observation. A schedule is a sequence of observations with associated starting time.

A schedule is feasible if: (i) each observation starts

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and ends within its VTW: $t_i \in [e_i; l_i - d_i]$; (ii) if observation i precedes observation j in the schedule, the time-gap between them is greater or equal to the transition delay: if $t_i < t_j$ then $t_j - t_i \geq d_i + \Delta_{i,j}(t_i)$; (iii) it terminates at or before the horizon: $\max_{i \in [1,n]} t_i + d_i \leq \tau$.

In this work, we use a utility-based framework where each observation is associated with a utility value u_i . The goal is then to find a feasible schedule that maximizes the cumulative utility of the observations it includes: $maximize \sum_{i \in [1,n]} u_i$.

2.2 Graph representation

In the EOSP, the start time of each observation and the transition durations are continuous, making the problem not strictly combinatorial. To address this, time is discretized, creating a large time-discretized graph representing the EOSP as a sequential decision problem. In this discrete graph, each candidate acquisition is represented for each possible discrete start time, and edges indicate possible transitions between observations. The graph is refined by pruning some superfluous edges to ensure optimal solutions, and schedules can be built using state-space approaches like Dijkstra or A* algorithms.

Our approach addresses the challenges of the discrete graph's complexity by deriving a much more compact continuous graph. In this continuous graph, each candidate observation is represented only once without specifying discrete start times. Edges between nodes represent feasible transitions from the discrete graph. The deep learning algorithm operates on this continuous graph, selecting acquisitions to insert into the schedule. The discrete graph is used to track decisions and update the continuous graph accordingly. This method leverages the continuous graph's compactness, making it suitable for graph neural networks, while still utilizing the discrete graph for detailed scheduling and simulation.

2.3 Sequential Decision Model

Our solution technique frames the process of building an optimal schedule for the EOSP as a reinforcement learning problem, using Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) algorithms to solve it. This approach treats the problem as a Markov Decision Process (MDP), where the state is the discrete EOSP graph, actions are possible successors of the last selected node, and the transition matrix describes deterministic transitions between states based on selected actions. The reward function is the utility value of the selected observation, aiming to maximize the total rewards. While the MDP is fully observable, the neural network operates

Figure 1: General Architecture

on a simplified continuous graph that approximates the problem, resulting in a partially observable MDP (POMDP) due to minor inaccuracies in transition durations.

2.4 Technical Solution

The global architecture is illustrated on Figure 1. In our reinforcement learning setup, the agent receives continuous graphs representing partial schedules and selects the next observations to schedule based on a policy aimed at maximizing cumulative utility. A simulator manages these graphs and provides the learner with the necessary data. The learner's policy, a stochastic mapping from states to actions, is trained on real-world problems to generalize well to unseen instances. The architecture involves processing input graphs through simple networks to produce node and edge embeddings, followed by a Message-Passing Graph Neural Network (MP-GNN) that extracts relevant features and generates action probabilities. The reinforcement learning algorithm then updates the parameters of the entire system, including embedders and the GNN, based on the rewards obtained.

2.4.1 Reinforcement Learning

We use the Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) algorithm [3], an on-policy actor-critic reinforcement learning method, augmented with action masking [4]. The actor, representing the current policy, selects actions, while the critic estimates the value of states to guide learning. PPO iteratively collects trajectory data, computes advantages by comparing sampled rewards with critic estimations, and updates the policy and critic parameters to maximize cumulative utility.

Reward shaping: A peculiar aspect of the EOSP instances we have to solve is that the utility of different acquisitions may vary by up to 8 degree of magnitude. In fact, acquisitions are grouped in 7 priority classes with value ranging from 1 to 10^8 . The utility of the

observations within a class of priority is equal to the value of that class, plus a term depending on the predicted cloud covering at the location of the acquisition. This generates instability in DRL algorithms (and in MDPs in general), as the low priority observations provide a reward that might be difficult to distinguish from the noise in reward statistics. In addition, the critic must learn very large values, starting from very low values at initialization, and following tiny gradient steps. This makes learning slow and inefficient.

We tried several approaches to handle this, including using a logarithmic scale and 2-hot encoding [5]. A simpler strategy that divides each individual reward by the average utility of all candidate observations has proved to work well in practice.

2.4.2 GNN Implementation

Our GNN implementation for the EOESP includes several key components:

- **Node Attributes:** Nodes in the continuous graph are labeled with visibility windows and satellite attitude statistics to inform the learner.
- **Graph Rewiring:** The input graph is edited to include reverse-precedence edges and self-loops, allowing information flow from future to present tasks (see [2]).
- **Embeddings:** Node and edge attributes are embedded using a learnable MLP, with an output dimension defined by a hyper-parameter.
- **Graph Pooling:** A global node connected to all other nodes is added to collect and integrate global information about the graph.
- **Action Selection:** Action probabilities are computed from concatenated logits of all GNN layers, normalized and masked to remove infeasible actions.
- **GNN:** The EGATConv from the DGL library [6] is used, featuring enriched graph convolutions [7] with edge attributes, 4 attention heads, and 10 layers, to yield values for nodes and the entire graph.

Dealing with different problem sizes: The GNN generates logits for each node, directly mapping nodes to actions regardless of the number of nodes or actions. The message-passing scheme is designed to be agnostic to the number of nodes, facilitating node regression based on reinforcement learning targets. This setup, while requiring careful implementation for data structures and batching, effectively handles varying problem sizes.

Connecting to PPO: In our implementation of PPO, we deviate from the generic structure of using a feature extractor followed by an MLP for the actor and critic. Instead, we maintain a one-to-one correspondence between nodes and actions, ensuring that the number of nodes remains a dimension in the data tensors. This approach reduces action selection to node regression, optimizing the learning process.

3 Results

3.1 Data

We use a set of real-life problems provided by our industrial partner, given in the form of the discrete-time graph. Since commercial data are sensitive, those scenarios are generated using statistics extracted from actual orders coming from commercial operations of Pléiades Neo. Since the requests are generated one by one following those statistics, it allows us to generate as many requests as we want for our problems. Fig. 2 shows an example of such generated request set.

In addition, one request can actually represent more than one satellite acquisition. The discrete-time graphs are then generated by computing the accessible requests on given orbits. The simulator uses this graph to compute and maintain the continuous-time graph.

Figure 2: Example request set

To provide intuition on the difficulty of the problem, table 1 shows number of elements on a few test problems and their representation as graphs.

3.2 Baselines

We compare our DRL approach to two solutions currently being used by Airbus DS, the satellite operator.

Acquisitions	Nodes		Edges	
	Discrete	Continuous	Discrete	Continuous
106	10297	106	835566	9273
308	52020	308	12598738	81244
508	46589	508	14842035	225398
809	59583	809	28015753	447945
1074	94071	1074	58343397	741634

Table 1: Number of elements on some problems

Greedy algorithm: It is the algorithm that is the currently used for real-world operations. It greedily selects acquisitions to add to the schedule based on the operational score (utility), and inserts them in the plan if possible.

RAMP: It is an implementation of Dijkstra search algorithm in the discrete graph [8]. Although based on an admissible algorithm (Dijkstra), RAMP is not guaranteed to find the absolute optimal schedule. This is due to the exclusion links between nodes of the discrete graph that represent the same task started at different times so as not to acquire the same image twice. Nevertheless, RAMP constantly provides the best known schedules on real problems. Unfortunately, its complexity prevents using it for real-time operations. Therefore, it is used as a reference in these simulation results.

3.3 Discussion

3.3.1 Single Problems

In initial experiments, our approach was tested on single problems to maximize the number of scheduled acquisitions, disregarding priority or utility. For a problem with 106 acquisitions, our model outperformed both the greedy algorithm and RAMP (top Fig. 3), demonstrating its capability to implement powerful policies. In a subsequent test focusing on maximizing cumulative utility, our system tackled a single problem with 88 candidate acquisitions. The results showed that our system not only outperformed the greedy algorithm but also matched the score of RAMP (Top Fig. 4), confirming the effectiveness of our architecture for the operational score setup.

3.3.2 Generalization

To evaluate generalization, our system was trained on 128 problems with approximately 100 acquisitions each and tested on 31 unseen problems of similar size, disregarding the full utility. The learning curve indicated that our model consistently outperformed the greedy algorithm but not RAMP (Bottom Fig. 3) on the test set, though proving its ability to

Figure 3: Unitary scores. Top: Training on a single problem of 106 acquisitions. Bottom: Test performance on 31 unseen problems, after training on 128 different problems.

Figure 4: Operational scores. Top: Training on a single problem with 88 acquisitions. Bottom: Test performance on 27 unseen problems, after training on 639 different problems.

Figure 5: Example of trajectory found by Wheatley on a 87 acquisitions problem compared to the Greedy trajectory.

generalize. In a second set of experiments considering utility, we trained on 639 problems and tested on 27 unseen problems. The learning curve and performance metrics demonstrated that Wheatley outperformed the deployed solution and closely approached the best-known performances (Bottom Fig. 4), validating its generalization capability in realistic, un-

Problem	Greedy	Ramp	Wheatley	W/G	W/R
100 (avg. 27)	510488439	605894711	605732913	1.1788	0.9901
300 (avg. 30)	202565994	263514132	239934939	1.2560	0.9420
508	142487	308355	221226	1.5526	0.7174
809	49000279	59000286	52000039	1.0612	0.8814
1074	2225103224	4124116197	2910000156	1.3078	0.7056
1591	307159	393214	220734	0.7186	0.5614
100 (dense) (avg. 10)	688941262	678921586	689578101	0.9996	1.0115

Table 2: Generalization scores

known problem setups. Figure 5 depicts trajectories found by Wheatley and the greedy algorithm. Acquisition requests are depicted in gray during their VTW. Manoeuvres between acquisitions are the colored arrows describing the satellite trajectory along time. We can see that Wheatley provides a better solution with shorter manoeuvres to avoid useless back-and-forth.

Table 2 shows comprehensive results for the agent learned on problems of size 100, evaluated on different sizes of problems with operational scores. Line 100 (dense) is evaluation on problems of size 100 with many conflicts, where RAMP performs worse than the greedy algorithm. W/G and W/R show relative score of wheatley compared to greedy and RAMP, respectively.

4 Conclusion

We have shown that DL-based approaches to the EOSP are competitive with the best-known techniques.

We are exploring several extensions to this work, including the use of lexicographic RL algorithms to better handle the large discrepancies in acquisition utility. Scheduling tasks by decreasing priority could ensure optimal schedules but requires non-chronological order, unlike our current implementation which relies on chronological insertion guided by the GNN.

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